

Development of an E-Module Learning “Sexual Education for Early Childhood” to Increase Adult Understanding in Protecting Children from Sexual Harassment

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Abstract:- This study aims to (1) produce e-module sexual education for early childhood that is appropriate to increase adult understanding of protecting children from sexual harassment. (2) Knowing the level of practicality of sexual education e-modules for early childhood to increase adult understanding in protecting children from sexual harassment. (3) Knowing the effectiveness of sexual education e-modules for early childhood to increase adult understanding in protecting children from sexual harassment. Research and Development area used as research technique, which used the ADDIE as development model (analyze, design, development, implementation, and evaluation). The subjects in this study are media experts, material experts and parents and teachers from PAUD Ma'arif and PAUD Cempaka. The instruments used in the study were e-module feasibility assessment questionnaires, e-module practicality assessment questionnaires and tests. Descriptive analysis used as data analysis. The results of the study showed that: (1) The e-module of sexual education for early childhood is declared feasible to increase adult understanding in protecting children from sexual harassment referring to the results of due diligence by media experts and material experts, all aspects are declared very feasibly. (2) The sexual education e-module for early childhood is declared practical by conducting smallgroup tests and large-group tests with very practical results. (3) Sexual education emodules for early childhood are declared effective in increasing adult understanding of protecting children from sexual harassment by conducting tests. The results of the pretest and posttest to calculate the effectiveness of the media using the gain score obtained a score of 0.75 (high), so it was concluded that sexual education e-modules for early childhood were effectively used to increase adult understanding in protecting children from sexual harassment.

Keywords:- Sexual education; early childhood; e-module.

I. INTRODUCTION

Early Childhood Education (PAUD) is a coaching effort aimed at children from birth to the age of six and is carried out through a process of providing educational stimuli to help physical and spiritual growth and development so that children have readiness to enter further education [1]. Education is a system consisting of input, process, and output, where the input in learning includes the education of students which is adapted to each level. Furthermore, the scope of a learning process includes teachers, media, modules/books, curriculum, and infrastructure 2 that adapt to the characteristics; while the output in education includes the results or benchmarks of a learning process [2].

Reported from [3], children who have experienced sexual harassment will have problems at school. They will feel mentally disturbed and have trouble concentrating in their daily life. This results in children being quiet, having difficulty socializing with peers, and experiencing difficulties in learning. The latest data is taken from [4], The Indonesian Child Protection Commission (KPAI) noted that from January to July 2022 there were 12 cases of sexual violence against children that occurred in educational institutions. Data taken from Kompas TV stated that the victims of sexual violence in the 12 cases totaled 52 children, of which 31 percent occurred in boys and 69 percent occurred in girls. The age range of the victims of sexual violence occurred in children aged around 5-17 years.

There are many factors that cause sexual violence against children, including the lack of understanding by adults, including parents and teachers, regarding sexual education. Adults still think that talking about sexual education is taboo and it is inappropriate to discuss it with children. Lack of attention from parents or teachers to children is the biggest factor in the occurrence of sexual violence. Sexual education in Indonesia is relatively minimal and has not been integrated evenly. Sexual education, which is still considered taboo by some people, is also the biggest reason for the high cases of sexual violence against children. Sexual education should have been given to children from an early age, this should at least become a basic understanding for children to know what to do when they have to be faced with a situation that leads to sexual violence.

The parents of Ma'arif and Cempaka PAUD students have occupational backgrounds as farmers, laborers and entrepreneurs. Farmers are 6 parents, workers are 2 parents and entrepreneurs are 10 parents. Judging from the educational background, most of the parents had 2 elementary school graduates, 3 junior high school students, 9 high school graduates, and 4 bachelor degree graduates. Looking at the educational and occupational backgrounds of the parents of Ma'arif and Cempaka PAUD students, researchers made observations on the children's daily lives. Referring to the background and characteristics of adults around PAUD Ma'arif and PAUD Cempaka, they are used to learning by discussing and receiving counseling. Quoting from Saifuddin (2010), the principles of adults in learning include creating a positive environment, creating social interaction, respect, and maintaining interest in learning. Based on the description above, the researcher developed the e-module as a facilitator for adults to learn, making the e-module a visualization or concrete form of discussions conducted as a continuation of learning.

Sexual education does not mean that it is not provided at all in the educational environment of PAUD Ma'arif and PAUD Cempaka, but that sexual education is only limited to an understanding of the differences between men and women, the toilets between boys and girls are differentiated, and how dress Muslim and Muslim women are good. In addition, although in PAUD Ma'arif and PAUD Cempaka there are books that facilitate understanding of sexual education, with most of them in the form of illustrated story books and posters explaining Muslim and Muslim women's clothing, this in fact cannot guarantee the delivery of education. sexuality for early childhood to the fullest.

The right way to provide sexual education for early childhood is through the media of pictures, posters, songs and games [5]. Looking at what the researchers have discussed previously, it can be concluded that developing e-learning modules is necessary to increase the understanding of adults in introducing sexual education in early childhood. This research resulted in an e-module "Sexual Education for Young Children". In developing sexual education e-modules for early childhood, research uses the area of learning technology "facilitating learning and improving performance". Educational technology itself is the study and practice of ethics to facilitate learning and improve performance by creating, using, and managing appropriate technological processes and resources [6].

II. THEORITICAL REVIEW

A. Early Childhood

Early age in children is the most important early period in the growth and development of children's lives. This golden age cannot be repeated or postponed, adults who understand these times will certainly not waste this opportunity. This is in line with the opinion of [7] which states that in the early stages of a child's growth, there will be maturation of physical and psychological functions to prepare the child for the next stage of development. Some people have so far labeled early childhood as children who have been able to register to attend early childhood

education. Whereas in essence early childhood has more understanding than that. In Law Number 20 of 2003 concerning the national education system, it explains the meaning of early childhood, namely the age from a child who has just been born to a child who has reached the age of six, or seen from formal schools, namely from a child born to kindergarten age.

B. Early Childhood Sexual Education

According to Carter V. Good in [8], quoted through the Basic Concepts of Early Childhood Education, explaining that education is a process of developing one's skills in the form of attitudes and behaviors that apply in society and is a social process in which a person is influenced by an environment that guided (eg school) so as to achieve social skills and develop personal. So that it can be concluded, the task of education is to guide humans, direct human growth and development from the early childhood education stage to the optimal ability of a human being. Sexual education is an effort to recognize names and functions of body parts, an understanding of gender differences and an understanding of the norms and values that exist in society [9].

Discussion in sexual education for early childhood will focus on providing children with understanding to deal with the bad possibilities that children will get as they grow. According to [10], the aim of efforts to prevent sexual abuse or violence against children in the field of sex education or education is for children to identify dangerous situations to prevent sexual harassment from occurring, and to teach children about various forms of touching that are not good. The purpose of sexual education is not to generate curiosity and want to try sex, but aims to provide understanding and education so that they can act according to religious, social and moral norms [9]. Quoting from [11], some of the advantages to be gained through sexual education are: (1) helping children understand biological topics such as growth in humans, puberty and pregnancy, (2) preventing children from sexual violence, (3) reduce feelings of guilt, shame and anxiety because of sexual acts, (4) prevent underage pregnancies, (5) prevent young adolescents from having sexual intercourse, (6) reduce or prevent cases of infection or disease due to sex, (7) help young people ask questions about the role of women and men in society.

C. The Role of Adults in Sexual Education

According to [12], the most important thing parents can do in providing sexual education is to change the way parents think about sexual education. All the behavior and ways of thinking of parents indirectly greatly affect the growth and development of children. Parents can provide a stimulus or basic understanding of sexual education by giving examples or telling stories while interacting with children. This kind of thing can only be done by parents, because parents are the closest people and the first people whose behavior will be followed or imitated by the child. According to [13], parents have a very important role in giving children an understanding of sexual education.

Teachers as educators in schools have the same responsibility as parents as intermediaries for providing sexual education. Teachers not only have the responsibility to provide sexual education to children, but teachers also have the responsibility to provide understanding to parents of the importance of sexual education. In accordance with [14], teachers have a very important role in carrying out learning in the form of sexual education for children. Sexual education that has been given by parents at home by providing stimulus or understanding in a way that is simple and easy for children to understand, will be maximized if this is balanced with materials that have been prepared by the teacher. The teacher prepares a learning plan by considering several aspects that are needed and suitable for early childhood. Besides that, the teacher must also prepare the final goals expected of a lesson.

D. Andragogy Learning Theory

Andragogy is defined by [15] as the science and art of helping adults learn. Meanwhile [16], defines andragogy as the science of adult learning, which in this case places more emphasis on the psychology of learning. So the conclusion drawn from these two meanings is that andragogy is a science and skill that can help adults to gain knowledge. According to [17] adult education is a realization of self-directed, intentional, systematic and sustainable learning. In addition to making oneself a director in learning, adult learning also makes other people a director in learning. Adult education is a process in which someone who is declared to be an adult is able to continue a learning activity, with the aim of changing understanding, skills, values and attitudes. In the educational process, andragogy is a systematic and sustainable matter, with the results to be achieved in the form of positive changes in understanding, skills, attitudes and values [18].

E. E-module

According to [19], e-modules are part of the development of modules, in the form of independent learning media that are systematically arranged and presented electronically. Quoting from [20], modules are learning materials that are designed systematically and refer to a particular curriculum and are packaged in the form of the smallest learning units. E-Modules were developed with the aim of making it easier for students to study material independently. It is hoped that with the development of the module, students can study it independently because it contains guidelines for use, objectives, methods, tools or media and their evaluation. E-Module in the big picture has a role as a tool to help students, so that learning becomes easier and can accelerate the learning process.

F. Development of E-Module Early Childhood Sexual Education

This e-module was developed to provide an understanding of sexual education to the community around PAUD Ma'arif and PAUD Cempaka, East Lampung. With the characteristics and background of the people who live around PAUD Ma'arif and PAUD Cempaka, researchers will adjust the development of this e-module product so that it is effective and easy to understand. According to [21], developing an e-module is the same as teaching through the intermediary of a book, an educator must know the background and characteristics of students so that they can adjust the use of language. The four basic understandings explained in this e-module are an understanding of sexual education, an introduction to body anatomy, an introduction to private areas on a child's body, as well as good and bad forms of touch that children might get in their daily lives.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Initial Product Development Results

This study aims to produce an e-module "sexual education for early childhood". Referring to the purpose of this development, the research method used is research and development. The development model used in developing this media is the ADDIE development model, consisting of the following stages:

➤ *Analysis Phase*

In the analysis phase, the researcher made several initial observations, including an analysis of user needs and an analysis of the characteristics of the user. This initial analysis activity was carried out on August 7, 2022, by observing and interviewing the community around PAUD Ma'arif and PAUD Cempaka.

➤ *Design Phase*

The steps that have been carried out before are then continued by starting to design the developed media. Planning is very important to make sexual education e-module media for early childhood interesting for adults in order to increase adult understanding of sexual education:

- Preparation of Sexual Education E-module Framework
- Learning Strategies
- Presentation of Teaching Materials
- Developing E-module Feasibility and Practical Quality Instruments.

➤ *Development Phase*

- E-module Media Compilation Prototype

Fig. 1: e-module creation design

- **Media Feasibility and Practicality Test**

Before being used in learning, the sexual education e-module prototype for early childhood children is first tested for its qualifications by media experts and material experts as well as a practicality test carried out by parents as users.

- **Implementation Phase**

At the implementation stage, the aim is to find out the effectiveness of the sexual education e-module for early childhood. Researchers conducted an effectiveness test on 26 respondents consisting of 18 parents and 8 teachers from PAUD Ma'arif and PAUD Cempaka. The effectiveness test in this study used two tests, namely the pretest and posttest. The pretest will be held on December 2, 2022 and the posttest will be held on December 17, 2022.

- **Evaluation Phase**

At the evaluation stage the researcher conducted 2 evaluation stages, the first was the phase before the media was implemented and the second was the phase after the media was implemented. In the first stage, the researcher evaluated the assessment by experts on sexual education e-module media for early childhood. The evaluation that was carried out next was an evaluation to determine the effectiveness of the sexual education e-module media for early childhood after the media was implemented.

B. Product Trial Results

Product trials were carried out from November to December 2022 in the surrounding community, especially parents and teachers of PAUD Ma'arif and PAUD Cempaka.

- **Media Member Validation Level**

The assessment by media experts includes two aspects, namely the Software Engineering (RPL) aspect and the visual communication aspect. The assessment was carried out by a media expert lecturer namely Dr. Ali Muhtadi, M.Pd. as a lecturer in the Postgraduate Program at Yogyakarta State University. According to the assessment of sexual education e-module media experts for early childhood, an average score of 4.6 out of 5 was obtained. The media that has been developed can be said to be "very appropriate" to be used to increase people's understanding of early childhood sexual education in accordance with the assessment. media expert.

- **Material Expert Validation Stage**

The quality of the material contained in the sexual education e-module for early childhood was assessed by material experts from the aspects of learning design, presentation of material, depth and breadth of material and metacognition. The evaluation of the e-module material was carried out by Prof. Dr. Harun, M.Pd., as a lecturer in Early Childhood Education. According to the assessment of material experts on sexual education e-module for early childhood, an average score of 5 out of 5 is obtained. The material contained in the media that has been developed can be said to be "very appropriate" to be used to increase adult understanding of early childhood sexual education according to the opinion of media experts. According to experts, this media material is suitable for use without revision.

- **Practicality Test Stage**

The practicality trial phase consists of small group trials and large group trials. Small group tests were conducted on 3 users, namely parents who have children aged 1-5 with an undergraduate education background. Parents respond to sexual education e-module media for early childhood. Referring to the results of processing small group test data, the data obtained was 4.4 out of 5 and included in the "very feasible" category. The comments obtained during the small group test are that the media that has been developed is very interesting to study. Sexual education e-modules for early childhood are considered to be able to help adults understand sexual education for early childhood. Large group test was conducted on 10 users. Respondents for the large group test were parents who had children aged 1-5 years, with undergraduate and postgraduate educational backgrounds. Referring to the table above, the results of data processing obtained were 4.6 out of 5 with the "very practical" category. From the results obtained through large group trials, the e-module of sexual education for early childhood can practically help adults to increase their understanding of early childhood sexual education.

➤ *Effectiveness Test Phase*

The effectiveness test was conducted on 26 respondents consisting of 18 parents and 8 teachers from PAUD Ma'arif and PAUD Cempaka. The purpose of the effectiveness test was to see an increase in adult understanding of early childhood sexual education. In the adult effectiveness test stage, parents and teachers are given a pretest to find out the initial knowledge of adults regarding sexual education for early childhood. The next stage after the pretest is to provide

sexual education e-modules for early childhood to increase adult understanding in protecting children from sexual crimes. After understanding the contents of the sexual education e-module for early childhood, users, namely parents and teachers, are given posttest questions to see if there is an increase in understanding sexual education for early childhood. The results of the calculations from the pretest and posttest of sexual education for early childhood will be described in the table below:

Variable	Score	
	Preset	Posttest
Lowest Value	49	79
The highest score	69	99
Average	58.2	89.6
Score Gain Score	0.75	
Gain Criterion	Height	

Table 1: Comprehension Test Results With Gain Score

According to the table above, the lowest score produced in the pretest was 49 and the highest score was 69 with an average value of 58.2. After the sexual education e-module media for early childhood is used by adults to increase their understanding, then a posttest is carried out

afterwards. The average score obtained through the posttest was 89.6, with the lowest score being 79 and the highest score being 99. Comparison of the pretest and posttest scores is also presented in the bar chart below:

Fig. 2: Comprehension test score graph

Based on the results obtained through the pretest and posttest or before and after distributing the media to users, the score for increasing adult understanding of early childhood sexual education is calculated using the gain score as follows:

$$g = (S_{Post} - S_{Pre}) / (S_{Max} - S_{Pre})$$

$$g = (89.6 - 58.2) / (100 - 58.2)$$

$$g = 31.4 / 41.8$$

$$g = 0.75$$

Based on the formula calculation using the gain score by looking at the previous data, the gain score data processing shows a value of 0.75 which is included in the "High" criteria. The results of data processing using the gain score show that there is an increase in understanding of parents and teachers after using the sexual education e-module for early childhood. Thus it can be concluded that the sexual education e-module for early childhood has a

high level of effectiveness to increase adult understanding of early childhood sexual education.

C. *Revision*

Revisions to the e-module refer to evaluations and suggestions from media experts and content experts.

➤ *Revision of Material Aspects*

Referring to the material expert's assessment of sexual education e-modules for early childhood, the media that has been developed gets an assessment of 5 out of 5. The comment written by the material expert in the assessment is "please use it", so that it becomes early childhood education e-module material suitable for use for field trials without revision.

➤ *Media Aspect Revision*

Referring to the assessment of media experts regarding sexual education e-modules for early childhood, several suggestions were obtained from media experts including the following:

- a) Changed the application settings from 1:1 to 16:9 to make the book appear larger on the screen

Before Revision

After Revision

- b) Change the font size to be larger for comfortable reading

Before Revision

After Revision

c) Adds an image illustration on the page

Before Revision

After Revision

Before Revision

After Revision

Before Revision

After Revision

Before Revision

After Revision

D. Final Product Review

This research and development aims to produce sexual education e-modules for early childhood to increase adult understanding in protecting children from sexual crimes. Final product studies include the following: This development research uses the ADDIE development model (Analyze, Design, Development, Implementation, Evaluation). In the analyze phase, several stages are carried out, namely needs analysis and user character analysis. A needs analysis was carried out to find out whether sexual education has been received by early childhood children who attend PAUD Ma'arif and PAUD Cempaka. The researcher also conducted an initial assessment of parents' knowledge of sexual education. Apart from that, the researcher also looked at the availability of media to convey sexual education in PAUD Ma'arif and PAUD Cempaka. At the user character analysis stage, it is carried out to determine the characteristics of early childhood sexual education e-module users, so that the development of this e-module can be adapted to the background of the e-module users themselves. The parents of Ma'arif and Cempaka PAUD students have occupational backgrounds as farmers, laborers and entrepreneurs. Farmers are 6 parents, workers are 2 parents and entrepreneurs are 10 parents. Judging from the educational background, most of the parents had 2 elementary school graduates, 3 junior high school students, 9 high school graduates, and 4 bachelor degree graduates.

The second stage is design, at this stage planning is very important to make sexual education e-module media for early childhood interesting so that it can increase adult understanding of sexual education. After going through the stages of analyzing the needs and characteristics of users, it was decided that sexual education for early childhood would be developed in the form of e-modules. The consideration made to decide on the use of e-modules is that learning can be done anywhere and anytime, the possibility of loss of teaching materials can also be minimized by using the e-module format. The next stage is designing sexual education e-modules for early childhood which contain introduction, content and closing. The design of this e-module is then followed by designing a flowchart and storyboard of the e-module being developed. The storyboard contains ideas or a big picture of sexual education e-modules for early childhood. Next is to develop sexual education e-modules for early childhood according to the previously designed flowcharts and storyboards. Flip HTML5 was chosen by researchers in developing the format of e-module sexual education for early childhood. This format was chosen because to access e-module sexual education for early childhood users do not need complicated devices or are required to download other applications as a support. In accessing the e-module in this format, users only need to open the link provided and can read the e-module easily and simply.

The e-modules produced are then tested for feasibility by media experts and material experts before being used by parents and teachers. The results of the media validation carried out by media experts produced a score of 4.6 out of 5 and were included in the very feasible category to use. Validation carried out by material experts produces a score of 5 out of 5 which is included in the qualifications that are very feasible to use. After conducting a feasibility test conducted by experts, the e-module sexual education media for early childhood was then tested for its practicality by conducting small group tests and large group tests. The small group test involved as many as 3 parents who had children aged 1-5 years with an undergraduate education background. The small group test resulted in a score of 4.4 out of 5 and was included in the very practical category. The large group test involved 10 parents who had children aged 1-5 years with undergraduate and postgraduate education backgrounds. The large group test resulted in a score of 4.6 out of 5 with that the e-module of sexual education for early childhood is in the very practical category to use.

The next stage of development is implementation. At the implementation stage the researchers tested the effectiveness of the sexual education e-module for early childhood. The effectiveness test was conducted on 26 respondents consisting of 18 parents and 8 teachers from PAUD Ma'arif and PAUD Cempaka. The effectiveness test is intended to see an increase in understanding by adults by using the sexual education e-module for early childhood that has been developed. The effectiveness test was carried out by giving pretest and posttest to 26 respondents. The pretest is given before the sexual education e-module for early childhood is disseminated to users. After the resulting media has been validated by media experts and material experts and passed the revision stage on the advice given by experts, the media is ready for use. The results of calculations using the gain score produce a score of 0.75 which is included in the High category. The results shown through data processing using a gain score indicate an increase in adult understanding of sexual education for early childhood before and after using the e-module. Thus it can be concluded that sexual education e-modules for early childhood are considered effective in increasing adult understanding of early childhood sexual education.

IV. CONCLUSION

Referring to the results of research and development of sexual education e-modules for early childhood, it can be concluded that:

- The e-module of sexual education for early childhood that can be used to increase adults' understanding of early childhood sexual education has the following characteristics: (1) This e-module describes clear and measurable goals. (2) This e-module only focuses on discussing sexual education for early childhood, written briefly, concisely and clearly in order to convey important and targeted knowledge. (3) This e-module can be studied without having to use it together with other media. (4) This e-module consists of the latest issues related to sexual violence, it is hoped that it will increase the willingness of adults to study sexual education e-modules

for early childhood. (5) This e-module uses simple language and is easy to understand, and is equipped with illustrations to facilitate understanding.

- Sexual education e-modules for early childhood are appropriate for use to increase adults' understanding of early childhood sexual education. Based on the due diligence by media experts and material experts, all aspects representing the media and material were declared very feasible. Data from the feasibility trial results from media experts showed a score of 4.6 out of 5 in the very feasible category, the results from the material expert showed a score of 5 out of 5 thus the e-module of sexual education for early childhood was categorized as very feasible to use. Data on the practicality of sexual education e-modules for early childhood were obtained from small group tests and large group tests. The data obtained from the small group test showed a score of 4.4 out of 5. The data obtained from the large group test was 4.6 out of 5. It can be concluded that this e-module is "very practical" for use in learning.
- Sexual education e-modules for early childhood are effectively used to increase adult understanding in protecting children from sexual crimes. Product effectiveness is obtained from tests carried out by users, the tests carried out include pretest and posttest. The results of the pretest given to users show an average result of 58.2, the results of the pretest show a result of 89.6. The data obtained is then processed using a gain score and produces a value of 0.75 which is included in the High classification. By looking at the results of the gain score, the e-module of sexual education for early childhood is considered effective in increasing adult understanding.

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